

“My book is different from the traditional reading experience. I didn't want it to be the sort of book that symbolises knowledge and configures readers as receivers of knowledge.”

Matthew Reynolds, Professor of English and Comparative Criticism at Oxford University

According to Reynolds, “*Prismatic Jane Eyre: Close-Reading a World Novel Across Languages*” was never going to be an ordinary book. Just as *Jane Eyre* is not just an English book – it has been translated into many different languages, with each translation creating shifts in interpretation, understanding, language, voice and style. There are now many Janes, says Reynolds, who led the *Prismatic Jane Eyre* research project, which culminated in an open access volume.

Reynolds collaborated with many academics from around the world and he wanted the book to reflect the international input and the nature of the work – that literature is not restricted to one language, one interpretation or one voice.

He said: “Reviewing all this work by translators and publishers in different locations is creative work. It's collaborative and creative, remaking and discovering new significances in new locations.”

Being open access and born digital, there was much more flexibility over the book's form, language and content. The different authors had more freedom to write in their own voice and style, and the text includes digital interactive maps and verbal animations.

Reynolds says this approach helps break down disciplinary and traditional academic silos, leading to greater creative expression.

Reynolds thinks publishing open access benefits research

It enables authors to explore the potential of digital

It breaks down barriers, encouraging interdisciplinary working

New ways of publishing encourage innovation and new research outputs

It encourages diversity of thinking